

Improvement in impact properties of laminated glass panels through surface treatment and silane coupling agent

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Abstract : In this paper, impact properties of the laminated glasses prepared through UV Curing method have been investigated. These are widely used in the automotive and construction industry in a variety of applications to enhance the strength and durability of the safety glasses as structural materials. UV Curable formulations comprising an organosilane as an adhesion promoter were developed and used as interlayers for laminated assemblies. Surface treatment of inner sides of the glass panes was performed chemically with the help of hydrofluoric acid at a temperature of 25 °C for 60 min. The falling weight test was used to analyze the impact strength of the glass laminates. Fractured surfaces of laminates were examined and compared with laminated samples prepared from unetched glass panes. Impact test results indicated that impact strength of the laminates was enhanced by surface treatment due to improved interface interaction between the interlayers and glass panes. Adhesion of the cured interlayer with the glass was also improved significantly as observed from the hammer test and boiling water test results.

Keywords : Silane coupling, laminated glass, chemical etching, impact resistance.

Introduction

Laminated glass imparts the strength to withstand attack by impacting objects since it provides a very efficient method of absorbing the localized kinetic energy of impact and has the ability to prevent splinters of glass flying on impact because of their strong adhesion to interlayer. The actual structure of glass like number of interlayer, glass plies and hence strength of laminated glass depends upon its application. In these laminates, polymeric interlayers are inserted between the glass panes, using soda lime glass, annealed glass or tempered glass (heat strengthened glass)^{1,2}. In the production of the glass plates there are processes which increase the strength of annealed glass. Heat treated glass possesses additional strength, impact resistance and resistance to thermal stresses. Annealed glass which has been heated to a temperature near its softening point and forced to cool rapidly under carefully controlled conditions is described as heat treated glass. Heat treated glass are classified as either fully tempered or heat strengthened. Building codes such as the Standard building code (SBCCI, 1985) suggest that under lateral pressure, the relative resistance of

heat strengthened glass is two times that of annealed glass of equal thickness and that of fully tempered glass is approximately four times that of annealed glass of equal thickness. When fully tempered glass breaks, the glass fractures into small, relatively harmless fragments. This phenomenon is called dicing. Using toughened glass can pose a security risk in some situations because of the tendency of the glass to shatter completely upon hard impact rather than leaving shards in the window frame. Combinations of annealed glass and tempered glass with polymeric interlayer are effective barriers against bullet impact^{3,4}. The fact that the strength of the glass may be enhanced by etching or other surface treatment to remove or modify surface faults and that the etched surface may subsequently be protected by coating or used in contact with a thermoplastic interlayer within a laminate has been documented for many years. Swiss patent specification⁵ 367942 and US patent⁶ 3,711,263 describes that how the strength of the glass is enhanced by etching the surface upto a depth of 80 or 20 microns respectively to remove surface defects. US patent⁷ 4,911,743 discloses strengthening of glass by chemical etching. An alternative ap-

proach to strengthen the glass is chemical toughening which gives the glass a chemically strengthened surface. The term chemically strengthened surface is used to encompass surfaces that have been strengthened either by ion exchange method or through chemical etching for example with hydrofluoric acid. Chemical toughening results in increased toughness compared with thermal toughening, and can be applied to glass objects of complex shape⁸. Chemical etching of the glass surface removes or reduces flaws which might serve as a site for the initiation of cracks in the glass. Etching techniques are most applicable for strengthening thermally toughened glass when the glass to be treated has a nominal thickness of at least 4 mm, so that too high proportion of the compressively stressed layer is not removed. Chemical etching is especially applicable to the protection of the glass plies which have been strengthened in other ways which result in their being vulnerable to surface damage, for example chemical strengthening through ion exchange method. In such chemically strengthened glass, the compression layers are quite thin, so that surface damage after such chemical strengthening may lead to significant reduction in strength.

Impact properties of laminated glass depends upon the thickness of interlayer, number of glass panes used, composition of the interlayer and compressive surface strength of the glass⁹. Glass laminates have been readily obtained by photocuring of acrylic adhesives consisting either of a liquid resin or a solid thermoplastic polymer^{10,11}. Numerous researchers have worked extensively on photopolymerization of UV curable systems¹²⁻¹⁷. UV Curing offers numerous environmental advantages with high production efficiencies leading to products with unique physical properties^{18,19}. In the present work laminated glasses have been prepared through UV Curing method using soda lime glass. The glass panes were chemically strengthened through etching. The inner surfaces of the glass panes used in the preparation of laminated glass panels were chemically etched with hydrofluoric acid (5%). The prepared laminated glasses were tested for impact properties using falling weight method and adhesion of the cured interlayers with the glass panes was also determined through hammer test and boiling water test. These

results have been compared with laminated assemblies comprising unetched glass panes.

Results and discussion

UV curable formulations :

Different UV curable formulations using diacrylate resin, acrylates, vinyl trimethoxy silane and photoinitiator were developed and four samples of laminated glass for each formulation were prepared through UV Curing method (Table 1). Laminated glass specimens with 2 mm and 3 mm thick interlayers were UV cured in 120 and 200 seconds respectively. The inner surfaces of two specimens (out of four) were chemically etched. The adhesion and impact resistance properties of these specimens were determined and compared, the data has been presented in Table 2 (Figs. 1-5).

Vinyl silane coupling with glass surface :

Vinyl silanes are used as adhesion promoters between organic polymers and mineral substrates²⁰. They possess exceptional reactivity in polymer composites, the adhesion of the cured polymers with glass is also improved with the incorporation of a suitable coupling agent. In the present work, vinyl trimethoxy silane is incorporated in the UV curable formulations as a coupling agent to enhance the adhesion and impact properties of the cured interlayer with glass. Reaction Scheme 1 represents the mechanism of silane coupling at the glass and polymer interlayer interface and as well its polymerization with acrylates. The alkoxy silanes react directly with -Si-OH groups of silica thereby forming -Si-O-Si- bonds without any requirement of prehydrolysis²¹.

Adhesion test :

Adhesion of the cured interlayer with the glass was checked with the help of Hammer test (Pummel test) and boiling water test. Table 2 summarizes the pummel values and boiling water test values along with sample codes. From the pummel values and boiling water test values it was observed that the laminated glass specimens (LGF₁2-LGF₅2) prepared by using F₁, F₂, F₃, F₄ and F₅ formulations possess good adhesion of the cured interlayer with glass. 70-80% of the glass remains adhered to the interlayer under hammer test and also no effect was found

Scheme 1. Bonding of vinyl silane with glass surface and acrylates.

under boiling water test. In these formulations as the concentration of the resin is decreased from F₁-F₅, the adhesion of the interlayer with glass is decreased as indicated from the pummel values. The laminated samples with etched inner surfaces were found to possess higher adhesion with glass.

Impact resistance test :

The prepared glass laminates has been tested for impact resistance by falling weight impact instrument designed and fabricated as described in the Experimental section. The weight of the ball was 0.225 kg and the height from which it was dropped was 4.83 m. From the known values of weight and height, the impact energy and the velocity of the ball were calculated using the

equations;

$$E = mgh \tag{1}$$

$$v^2 - U^2 = 2gh \tag{2}$$

The impact energy was 10.650150 J and the velocity of the ball hitting the specimen was 9.729748 m/sec.

The photographs of falling weight impact test of prepared laminated glasses are shown in the Figs. 1 to 5. All the data related to impact test of the specimens is summarized in Table 3. The laminated glasses prepared by using F₁ formulation, LGF₁2-LGF₁2E are shown in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1(a), a large amount of glass was removed from the point of hit and its radius is greater than the radius of the ball (38 mm). The specimen was failed, again the specimen LGF₁2E (Fig. 1(b)) whose inner surfaces were

Table 1. List of the laminated glass specimens code, formulation used, thickness of the interlayer and thickness of the specimens prepared by UV Curing

Sr. No.	Laminated glass specimen code	Formulation used	Thickness of interlayer (mm)	Thickness of specimen (mm)	Chemical etching
1.	LGF ₁ 2	F ₁	2	9	No
2.	LGF ₁ 2E	F ₁	2	9	Yes
3.	LGF ₁ 3	F ₁	3	10	No
4.	LGF ₁ 3E	F ₁	3	10	Yes
5.	LGF ₂ 2	F ₂	2	9	No
6.	LGF ₂ 2E	F ₂	2	9	Yes
7.	LGF ₂ 3	F ₂	3	10	No
8.	LGF ₂ 3E	F ₂	3	10	Yes
9.	LGF ₃ 2	F ₃	2	9	No
10.	LGF ₃ 2E	F ₃	2	9	Yes
11.	LGF ₃ 3	F ₃	3	10	No
12.	LGF ₃ 3E	F ₃	3	10	Yes
13.	LGF ₄ 2	F ₄	2	9	No
14.	LGF ₄ 2E	F ₄	2	9	Yes
15.	LGF ₄ 3	F ₄	3	10	No
16.	LGF ₄ 3E	F ₄	3	10	Yes
17.	LGF ₅ 2	F ₅	2	9	No
18.	LGF ₅ 2E	F ₅	2	9	Yes
19.	LGF ₅ 3	F ₅	3	10	No
20.	LGF ₅ 3E	F ₅	3	10	Yes

Table 2. Shows adhesion of different interlayers with glass through boiling water test and Pummel test

Sr. No.	Laminated glass specimen code	Pummel value		Value on boiling water scale	
		Nonetched specimens	Etched specimens	Nonetched specimens	Etched specimens
1.	LGF ₁ 2	8.0	8.5	1	1
2.	LGF ₂ 2	8.0	8.5	1	1
3.	LGF ₃ 2	7.5	8.0	1	1
4.	LGF ₄ 2	7.5	8.0	1	1
5.	LGF ₅ 2	7.0	7.5	1	1

chemically itched was also failed in this test as ball passed through the sample leaving behind a large hole. On comparing the weights from the underside of the specimens, it was found that a low amount of broken glass was obtained from the underside of the etched specimen. When the thickness of the interlayer was increased from 2 mm to 3 mm in the specimen LGF₁3 (Fig. 1(c)), the radius of the hole was approximately 38 mm and number of fragments was also reduced. Furthermore the weight from the underside is 0.072 kg as compared to 0.126 kg from

LGF₁2. The chemically etched specimen LGF₁3E (Fig. 1(d)) showed better results as its radius is less than 38 mm and weight from underside is 0.054 kg which is minimum among the four specimens of F₁ formulation. Here the ball passes through the specimen not because of hole but due to fragmentation in the laminated specimen.

These results emphasize that chemical etching of the inner surfaces of the glass panes used in the preparation of laminated assembly is increasing the adhesion of the interlayer with the glass by increasing the available sur-

Fig. 1. Falling weight impact test of UV curable interlayer glass laminates prepared from formulation F_1 : (a) LGF₁₂, (b) LGF_{12E}, (c) LGF₁₃, (d) LGF_{13E}.

face area for bonding. These results were found consistent with the pummel values of etched and non etched laminated glass specimens. On comparing the specimens of 2 mm and 3 mm thick interlayers, it can be seen that the amount of impact energy distribution is increased when the thickness of the interlayer is increased, which is evident from the radii of the hole and weight from the underside of the specimens. In Fig. 2 laminated glass specimens prepared by using F_2 formulation are shown. Similar energy distribution patterns are shown by these specimens, while on comparing the weights from the underside of the specimens, these were found lower than respective specimens prepared from F_1 formulation of the first set of formulations. The specimens of F_2 formulation possess lower pummel values than F_1 specimens.

Falling weight impact test results of UV curable interlayer glass laminates prepared from formulation F_3 i.e. LGF₃₂, LGF_{32E}, LGF₃₃ and LGF_{33E} are shown in Fig. 3.

Comparatively nice energy distribution patterns were found in all the specimens. The ball pierced all the specimens and weights of broken glass from the underside are given in the Table 3. On observing the photographs of these specimens, it was found that the number of crack lines in these laminated assemblies is greater than previous specimens prepared from F_1 and F_2 formulations and distance between these energy distribution lines is de-

Fig. 2. Falling weight impact test of UV curable interlayer glass laminates prepared from formulation F_2 : (a) LGF₂₂, (b) LGF_{22E}, (c) LGF₂₃, (d) LGF_{23E}.

creasing gradually from specimen LGF₃₂ to LGF_{33E}. The two parameters i.e. chemical etching and thickness of the interlayer are showing the same patterns as discussed above in case of F_1 and F_2 formulations. Out of four specimens, three specimens possess radii of the hole less than 38 mm indicating that impact strength of the laminated glass specimens is increasing as we are moving from F_1 - F_3 formulation which is further confirmed by weight of the broken glass from the underside of the laminated glass specimens. The underside weights of tested laminated glass specimens of F_3 formulation are smaller than of F_1 and F_2 specimens. In the specimens LGF_{32E}, LGF₃₃ and LGF_{33E}, the ball passed through due to fragmentation of laminated assemblies as radius of the hole is less than the radius of the ball.

On examining the photographs of falling weight impact test of laminated glass specimens prepared by using F_4 formulation, laminated assemblies were found to possess good impact strength and laminated specimens LGF₄₃ and LGF_{43E} were stopped the ball on their surface and hence these specimens passed the falling weight impact test by absorbing 10.65 J of energy at a velocity of 9.72 m/sec (Fig. 4(c), (d)). Laminated specimens LGF₄₂ and LGF_{42E} when compared with LGF₃₂ and LGF_{32E} specimens, showed better results in terms of radius of the hole, weight of broken glass from underside of the specimen and number of fragments. No hole was found in all

Fig. 3. Falling weight impact test of UV curable interlayer glass laminates prepared from formulation F_3 : (a) LGF₃2, (b) LGF₃2E, (c) LGF₃3, (d) LGF₃3E.

the four specimens prepared by using F_4 formulation. The impact energy distribution patterns are also nice. The number of energy distribution lines is maximum in these specimens and also these lines are very closely spaced.

In LGF₄3 specimen (Fig. 4(c)) the mark of the hit of the ball can be seen and the energy distribution lines originates from the periphery of this mark. On the contrary, in the laminated specimen LGF₄3E (Fig. 4(d)) whose inner surfaces are chemically etched, there is not even a mark of hit of the ball in the center. A tree like energy distribution pattern is shown. The impact energy could be absorbed at any point of the entire structure of the laminated glass specimen well away from the point of impact²². Cantwell and Morton proposed a pine tree damage pattern for the impact induced matrix cracks in thick and thin thickness laminated composites, respectively²³. Specimen LGF₄3E shows pine tree like damage pattern, which is in agreement with the study of Cantwell and Morton. These are the best results among the LG specimens prepared from all UV curable formulations. It was observed that as we are increasing the monomer concentration from F_1 (19.35%) to F_4 (41.86%), results obtained under impact testing are improving from fully pierced specimens to the specimens which have passed this test. So whether this will continue further, to study

Fig. 4. Falling weight impact test of UV curable interlayer glass laminates prepared from formulation F_4 : (a) LGF₄2, (b) LGF₄2E, (c) LGF₄3, (d) LGF₄3E.

this laminated specimens by using F_5 formulation were prepared and tested for impact under falling weight impact test. The photographs of LGF₅2-LGF₅3E are shown in Fig. 5. These specimens were failed under this test as the ball pierced all these specimens. Again the specimens with 3 mm thick interlayer showed better results in terms

Fig. 5. Falling weight impact test of UV curable interlayer glass laminates prepared from formulation F_5 : (a) LGF₅2, (b) LGF₅2E, (c) LGF₅3, (d) LGF₅3E.

Table 3. Summarized data of falling weight impact test of UV cured laminated glass specimens prepared by using F₁-F₅ formulations; impact energy 10.65 J, velocity 9.72 m/sec

Sr. No.	Designation of laminated glass specimen	Wt. of laminated assembly (kg)	No. of fragments	Radius of hole at the point of hit (mm)	Wt. from underside of LG specimen (kg)	% Wt. from underside of LG specimen
1.	LGF ₁ 2	1.830	5	> 38	0.126	6.88
2.	LGF ₁ 2E	1.815	5	> 38	0.101	5.56
3.	LGF ₁ 3	1.876	4	≈ 38	0.072	3.83
4.	LGF ₁ 3E	1.870	4	< 38	0.054	2.88
5.	LGF ₂ 2	1.821	5	> 38	0.110	6.04
6.	LGF ₂ 2E	1.820	5	> 38	0.082	4.50
7.	LGF ₂ 3	1.873	5	≈ 38	0.061	3.25
8.	LGF ₂ 3E	1.862	4	< 38	0.048	2.57
9.	LGF ₃ 2	1.893	4	> 38	0.092	4.86
10.	LGF ₃ 2E	1.802	4	< 38	0.079	4.38
11.	LGF ₃ 3	1.861	4	< 38	0.038	2.04
12.	LGF ₃ 3E	1.859	4	< 38	0.030	1.61
13.	LGF ₄ 2	1.826	2	No hole	0.015	0.82
14.	LGF ₄ 2E	1.810	2	No hole	0.012	0.66
15.	LGF ₄ 3	1.926	-	No hole	-	-
16.	LGF ₄ 3E	1.919	-	Not even mark of hit	-	-
17.	LGF ₅ 2	1.832	3	≈ 38	0.047	2.56
18.	LGF ₅ 2E	1.830	3	< 38	0.031	1.69
19.	LGF ₅ 3	1.886	4	≈ 38	0.028	1.48
20.	LGF ₅ 3E	1.882	3	< 38	0.019	1.00

of hole radius and weight of broken glass from the underside of the specimens than 2 mm interlayer specimens. However the impact test results of F₅ formulation were better than the previous formulations (F₁, F₂ and F₃). The order of performance of laminated specimens under falling weight impact test among UV curable formulations is as follows :

$$F_4 > F_5 > F_3 > F_2 > F_1$$

Experimental

Materials and characterization :

(a) Glass :

Glass used in the present work is the soda lime glass which was obtained from Krishna Glass Emporium, Meerut city. It contains 74% silica by weight, 13% Na₂O (obtained from soda ash), 10.5% CaO (generally obtained from limestone), 1.3% Al₂O₃, 0.3% K₂O, 0.2% SO₃, 0.2% MgO, 0.01% TiO₂, and 0.04% Fe₂O₃. The glass transition temperature and coefficient of thermal expansion

of soda lime glass is 573 °C and 9 ppm/K ~ 100–300 °C. Its refractive index was 1.518 and Young's modulus and Shear modulus at 20 °C was 72 GPa and 29.8 GPa respectively.

(b) Chemicals :

Divinylester resin or epoxy diacrylate was used as functionalized oligomer which was synthesized through the reaction of DGEBA (diglycidal ether of Bisphenol A) with acrylic acid below 90 °C for 4–5 h in the presence of triphenyl phosphine used as catalyst. The DGEBA used was procured from Singhal Chemicals and was of LY556 grade. It was transparent with specific gravity 1.15–1.20 g/ml and viscosity 5–8 Pas at 25 °C. Acrylic acid (99%, LR grade) was obtained from G. S. Chemicals P. Ltd. and was stabilized with 0.02% hydroquinone monomethyl ether. Triphenyl phosphine was obtained from CDH Chemicals and used as such without further purification. Methyl methacrylate (99%, LR grade) stabilized with 0.01% quinol was procured from G. S. Chemical lab and

Allied Industries, Bombay. Vinyl trimethoxysilane (98%) was procured from Sigma Aldrich. Hydrofluoric acid (48%) was procured from Qualigens fine chemicals (ExcelaR) and its density was 1.15–1.18 g/cm³. Among many commercial photoinitiators we selected Irgacure 184 from CIBA because of its high initiation quantum yield and low coloration of photoproducts.

UV curable formulations :

Low molecular weight acrylates were used in these formulations to adjust the viscosity of the formulation used as interlayer material. The properties of the interlayer, such as hardness, flexibility, solvent resistance and impact strength are determined by the composition of acrylate resins¹¹. The synthesized divinyl ester resin is highly viscous (mol. wt. 500 g) and need to be diluted with monomers in order to lower the resin viscosity. Acrylic acid and methyl methacrylate were employed as reactive diluents. Small amounts of an organosilane (vinyl trimethoxysilane) were added to most formulations to improve adhesion. The UV curable formulation contained 51%–80% oligomer, 20%–49% monomer, 0.1% silane and 3% photoinitiator (1-hydroxy cyclohexyl-phenyl ketone) (Table 4). All the ingredients were weighed and mixed thoroughly with the help of manual glass stirrers. The formulations were prepared one week in advance to their application to the substrate. These formulations are sensitive to light and hence these were kept in black colored containers and the beakers were also covered with black paper while using them in the preparation of laminated glass or casting of the films.

Preparation of laminated glass samples :

Though there are several techniques that have been developed for preparation of laminated glasses but in this

work we have used Hand Layup technique which is the simplest technique till date and also because the production volume is very low, Hand Layup technique is preferred. Glass laminates of dimensions 300 × 300 mm was prepared for the developed formulations by using two glass panes of 3.5 mm thickness each.

Cleaning of glass :

The glass panes were first thoroughly washed with water and then cleaned with glass cleaner, dry in air and then subjected to chemical etching with HF or laminated as per procedure described in the forthcoming section.

Chemical etching with HF :

The etching was carried out using aqueous HF preferably a concentration of 5% by weight, since the more concentrated acid has a tendency to etch the glass unevenly resulting in a roughened surface, while the use of weaker acids extends the etch time necessary to remove the desired amount of glass. The glass panes were immersed in aqueous HF (5%) for 60 min at 25 °C. After immersion in HF solution, the glass panes were washed in tap water, and then in deionized water and allowed to dry in air.

Filling of liquid formulation in the cavity between two glass plates :

The two chemically strengthened glass panes were then joined with the help of a two side adhering tape in such a manner so that the prepared formulation can be filled in between the two glass panes. The tape serves two purposes; it acts as a barrier that confines the resin until it is cured and it helps to set the interlayer thickness. The tapes of 3 mm and 2 mm thickness were used to prepare glass laminates. The formulation is then injected into the cavity and the whole assembly is subjected to UV Curing. Care should be taken to ensure that there must be no air bubbles left in the filled sample. If there any bubbles are present then they are gradually removed with time on vertical placement of the glass assembly in the designed frame. This frame has screws on two sides to hold the filled glass assembly and also any leakage of the formulation is also avoided.

UV Curing of the glass laminate :

The prepared assemblies with liquid interlayer were cured under UV radiation by using four Philips TL-D

Table 4. Composition of the formulations developed by using divinylester resin (VER); methylmethacrylate (MMA); acrylic acid (AA); Irgacure, that has been used for preparing UV cured glass laminates

Sr. No.	Designation	VER (g)	AA (g)	MMA (g)	Organosilane (Wt. %)	Irgacure (Wt. %)
1.	F ₁	100	12	12	0.1	3
2.	F ₂	100	24	24	0.1	3
3.	F ₃	100	30	30	0.1	3
4.	F ₄	100	36	36	0.1	3
5.	F ₅	100	48	48	0.1	3

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18W BLB UV tubes (made in Holland) arranged horizontally, two on each side in a UV chamber of dimensions $25 \times 15.5 \times 21$ inch. The time required to cure the sample completely was found in the range of 2–5 min depending upon the thickness of the interlayer.

Testing of laminated glasses :

The prepared glass laminates were tested for adhesion of interlayer with glass and impact resistance through falling weight method using impact instrument designed according to IS-2553-1971.

Adhesion test :

Pummel test was used to measure interlayer adhesion to glass. For Hammer test (Pummel test) twelve inch square glass laminates with 2 mm thick interlayer were prepared. The glass laminates were placed in a $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ refrigerator for at least 2 h. After removal from the refrigerator, the laminates were placed on a metal substrate and hit repeatedly with a 16 oz hammer to break the glass. All broken glass unadhered to the interlayer was then removed. The amount of glass left adhered to the interlayer was visually compared with a set of standards of known pummel scale and a pummel value for each sample was assigned, ranging from a pummel value of 0 (no adhesion, no glass adhered) to 10 (high adhesion, 100% of the glass adhered).

Boiling water test was also used to check the interlayer adhesion to glass and also water resistance. For this test laminated glass specimens of dimensions 4×4 inch were prepared. 20 mg of each formulation was dispensed on a glass sheet of 3.5 mm thickness and another sheet of glass was placed carefully over this sheet in such a manner that no air bubble entrapped between the sheets and then exposed to UV radiation. The specimens were kept in boiling water for 3 h and then withdrawn, dried and examined and the degree by which the adhesive layer has been affected is measured on the scale 0-7 determined as follows :

- (1) No effect.
- (2) Slightly affected at corners of sample only.
- (3) Very narrow band affected around periphery of the sample.
- (4) Affected band not exceeding about 2.5 mm wide around periphery parallel to sides.

(5) Width of affected areas extending upto 5 mm in from sides of the sample.

(6) Width of affected areas extending upto 8 mm in from sides of the sample.

(7) Seriously affected : only small area in middle of sample left unaffected.

Impact resistance :

Impact tests are designed to measure the resistance to failure of a material to a suddenly applied force. The test measures the impact energy or the energy absorbed prior to fracture. Impact energy is a measure of work done to fracture a test specimen. When the striker impacts the specimen absorbs energy until it yields. At this point the specimen begins to undergo plastic deformation and continues to absorb energy then fracture occurs. The falling weight impact test is most commonly used to evaluate the impact toughness of the materials. It involves dropping a weight in the vertical direction. It is unidirectional with no preferential direction of failure. Failures originate at the weakest point in the sample and propagate from there. When the specimen can absorb no more energy then failure occurs. The laminated samples (300×300 mm) were tested for impact resistance with the help of impact instrument which is designed as per clauses 4.3.4 and 6.2.3 mentioned in IS : 2553-1971. In this testing a laminated safety glass is given a sudden punch and fragments from the undersurface are collected and weighed. There is a square hardwood frame having dimensions such that the test specimen rests symmetrically on the frame and there shall remain unsupported 290×290 mm of the specimen. An electromagnet system has been used for dropping the ball freely from a height of 4.83 m so as to strike the specimen within 25 mm from its center. A hardened steel ball with a diameter of 38 mm and weighing about 225 g is used for the test. The laminates are held in square hardwood frame, which is placed on the ground and the hardened steel ball was dropped from the prescribed height in such a way that it hits the test specimen.

Conclusion

The penetration resistance of laminated glass is controlled primarily through the monomer concentration in the developed UV curable formulation. However a remarkable increase in the impact strength of the laminates

was observed in the surface treated glass laminates. Adhesion of the interlayer with glass is a key factor in preventing the scattering of glass splinters in the event of breaking. In the present study it has been concluded that surface treatment is enhancing the adhesion properties significantly as evident from the data obtained through hammer and boiling water test. In terms of manufacturing of the product, the production process is very fast, cost effective and environmentally friendly as UV curable formulations are VOC compliant and this technology is the best available control technology according to US Environment Protection Agency (EPA).

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